

The Meaning of It All – 8T

"The gleam in your eye tells me you have an idea." René Goscinny.

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Abstract:

The paper is meant for individuals who desire non-technical treatment of the 8T. In addition, the paper purpose is to be a general overview of the new framework. The author shares his views upon the construction of the 8T, the scope of phenomena it can reason and what was the truly hardest part in building this entire new theory.

Introduction

Our universe is really an entity called a manifold, which has two components, one on which we are living in, and another one, 'separated' or underlining it. We live on the metric space. This manifold has areas, which are highly curved; those areas do not change over time and yield outward pressure or acceleration, in time independent rate, outward from them. That is in this framework what is known "dark energy". In addition, we have the equation for describing it. That was the first innovation. All we care about in this framework is what the manifold does; we do not describe the motion of a particle, as they are not part of the theory. Particles in the 8T framework, and matter in particular is a result of variations of the manifold, those variations are random and they turn into matter, by mathematical proof. If the manifold experience a net variation (or net curvature), which are a prime numbers in the theory, the result is a force or a Boson propagation such as a photon for example. We have calculated the magnitude of the electric force based on the second element, weak interaction, and concluded that it is an infinite series, we have an equation which has the first two magnitudes right and an infinite set of testable predictions.

Thus, we reached the second major simplification in the theory. There are infinite force particles known as Bosons. One Boson for each prime number. The next Boson should stand at ratio $1/850$ when compared with the strong interaction. It is a major simplification for couple of reasons. First, it eliminates the gap between the gravitational coupling and the electric. There is an infinite amount of bosonic fields, generated by the same element, called the majestic three. Taken from that point of view, the second point is that we can reason the rapid formation of galaxies. The coupling constants series than allows us to answer one of the hardest questions, why there are only four forces? And the answer is – there is not. One arbitrary number less than any other theory. In this framework, we saw that nature is really the interplay or ratio between total manifold variations to the net variations. We saw that total variations grow much faster than the net. That is the reason as the total grows bigger and bigger, the net is a smaller and smaller portion of the whole. The ultimate test of the theory is whether there is a fifth force of nature who stand at the magnitude of $1/850$ relative to the strong. The third major simplification is revolving around the question of the masses. In our framework, we regard mass as curvature converging inward, same as force but inverse in the direction. By manipulation of the masses of the families, the 8-theory predicts that there are infinite families forming.

Their mass is much smaller than our so-called first generation, 8T was able to predict exactly A range in which the total mass of the forth would be around. 55-56 times lighter than the first family. Such prediction is a major simplification. First, it eliminates the question of "why three families?" Second, it provides a new possible answer for the issue of dark matter and invisible mass, and the concludes an interesting surprise – **third family (T-B) is the first family**. These are the major simplifications made by the 8T. We have three main equations to describe them, and exact prediction regarding the next element in the coupling constants series and the family series. It is the only theory with equation for dark energy, and the only theory that puts the coupling constants known to us under one equation. It has more than those simplifications but writing about those is beyond the scope of this paper. The theory provides a spectra of beautiful insight, as an example, we always wondered how would extra dimensions looks like. 8T showed that the structure of the multiverse is an infinite packet of universes interacting with other via areas of extremum curvatures, and for a resident of the distinct manifold, **our dimensions are the higher dimensions**. Of course the opposite is true as well. We are now able to probe into the structure of Quantum gravity using the primordial series, and prove that The great Dirac was right, when suggested that the gravitational coupling constant is not a constant at all. The 8T construction allows us to correlate the "dark energy" to flatness, two major features of the universe, all in one equation.

In other words, it is hard to find a question that 8T cannot shed light upon, it can only do so as it is so simple and concise, it contains an handful of equations which we use in different ways and forms again and again. The most difficult part in the creation of the 8T was making the actual derivation of the primorial, i.e. the coupling constants series. Meaning that the hard part was building the theorems and the pre-equation ideas, these were merely a result of imagination, creativity, and a large amount of boldness and believing in this radical beauty of primes that somehow has to be related to a final theory, which until proven correct was in matter of a guess. Boldness as those ideas could have been (very high chance) wrong, leading to wrong coupling magnitudes. However, after the third coupling term was calculated to be exactly on point with experiment, the range of ideas and questions 8T made using the idea and not necessarily the actual equation was and still unlimited, and reached almost one hundred and sixty pages. 8T reasoned for the unlimited terms in the series for the fast formation of galaxies, as each coupling term is a curvature of prime amount causing matter to cluster, we are now able to explain the spirals of galaxies and the sphere shape of stars, the homogenous structure of the universe and the duality of particles and waves as few examples. All this using the primorial, **one equation** that yielded the series:

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots$$

One does not have to be a physicist nor mathematician to see the beauty of such an infinite series. As the great Paul Dirac once stated about another giant of history, Albert Einstein: "he always asked: If I was god, was I making the world like this? And according to the answer he would decide whether he liked a particular theory or not". Einstein was right, the final mathematical series of a unified theory of physics is also among the most beautiful and the most simple we have seen. Most importantly, it showed that **nature is governed by reason**, and **those numbers were not chosen randomly**, and **that** is the real source of beauty of this whole 8T construction, the ability to clearly reason, reason herself.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series – 8 Theory" In: (2021)

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